

A highly selective spectrophotometric determination of niobium(V) using 6-chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as a complexing agent and chloroform as an extractant

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A simple, rapid, highly selective and sensitive method for the spectrophotometric determination of niobium(V) in trace amounts is presented, employing 6-chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CFHB) as a ligand for the complexation of the metal ion and extracting the 1 : 2 (M : L) coloured complex into chloroform from 4 M HClO₄ solution. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.32–1.25 mg ml⁻¹ Nb^V. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 410 nm are 2.79×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0033 µg Nb cm⁻², respectively. The method is free from the interference of large number of elements including molybdenum, tungsten, tantalum and platinum metals. The proposed system handles the analysis of several samples of varying complexity satisfactorily.

Thiocyanate^{1,2} either in an aqueous acetone medium or after extraction of the complex, bromopyrogallol red (BPR)¹, 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR)¹ and hydrogen peroxide² have been used frequently for the spectrophotometric determination of niobium(V) in different acidic media. Though the methods are quite sensitive¹, they suffer from large number of interferences especially from Ti, V, Mo, W, Pt, Re, U and Ta and also are time consuming as the complex requires more than 1 h for full colour development. In case of thiocyanate, rigorous adjustment of parameters, viz. SnCl₂, HCl and SCN is required as their concentration greatly affects the intensity of the colour and reproducibility of the results. All these methods recommend measurement of absorbance in aqueous medium which is otherwise susceptible to interferences from many other coloured ions. The recently used hydroxyflavone^{3–5}, hydroxamic acid⁶ and 2-(2-pyridylazo)-5-diethylaminophenol (PADAP)^{7,8} derivatives and Rhodamine B⁹ for the purpose also suffer from the same disadvantages. Accordingly, a new hydroxyflavone such as 6-chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CFHB) has been introduced as a complexing agent for Nb^V which makes the method more rapid, highly selective, accurate and sensitive.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance : In acid solution, niobium(V) formed a yellow complex with CFHB which was extractable into chloroform. The effect of different acids on the absorbance of the Nb^V complex in chloroform was studied at 4 M acid and it was found that the ab-

sorbance of the complex decreased in the order HClO₄ > HCl > H₂SO₄ > CH₃COOH > H₃PO₄. Therefore, HClO₄ was preferred for further work.

Effect of various organic solvents on absorbance of Nb^V-complex : Various organic solvents had been tried as extractants for the metal complex. The extraction behaviour (in terms of absorbance) was found to decrease in the order : chloroform > dichloromethane > benzene > toluene > isoamyl alcohol > isobutyl methyl ketone > ethyl acetate > carbon tetrachloride > 1,2-dichloroethane. As chloroform gave maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was chosen as the most suitable extractant. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform, under optimum conditions gave quantitative (100%) extraction of Nb^V-CFHB complex.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorption spectrum of the complex in chloroform showed maximum between 400–420 nm where the reagent blank had negligible absorbance. The coloured Nb^V-CFHB complex was stable for more than 2 h in chloroform at 410 nm.

Effect of concentration of HClO₄, CFHB, temperature and equilibration time : The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 2.4–4.9 M HClO₄, 0.9–2.2 ml of CFHB (0.4% in acetone), 25–35° temperature and 45–420 s equilibration time for ≤ 13 µg Nb^V per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1).

Beer's law range, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and composition of the complex : Beer's law was

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the Nb-complex

Temperature (°C) ^a	20	23	25–35	37	40	45		
Absorbance	0.270	0.280	0.300	0.275	0.260	0.220		
HClO ₄ (M) ^b	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.6	2.0	2.4–4.9	5.2	5.6
Absorbance	0.110	0.170	0.200	0.220	0.270	0.300	0.270	0.210
0.4% CFHB (ml) ^c	0.4	0.8	0.9–2.2	2.5				
Absorbance	0.050	0.210	0.300	0.270				
Equilibration time (s) ^d	0	5	10	15	30	45–420	600	
Absorbance	0.050	0.180	0.190	0.200	0.240	0.300	0.295	

Conditions : ^aNb^V = 10 µg, HClO₄ = 4.0 M, 0.4% CFHB = 1 ml, equilibration time = 1 min, solvent = chloroform, temperature = variable; ^btemperature = 33°, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in HClO₄ concentration; HClO₄ = 4.0 M, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in CFHB concentration, also ^c6-chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CFHB); ^d0.4% CFHB in acetone = 1.0 ml, other conditions being the same as in (c) except for the variation in equilibration time.

valid in the niobium concentration range of 0–1.3 µg ml⁻¹. However, the optimum range of determination of niobium as evaluated from Ringbom plot was found to be 0.32–1.25 µg ml⁻¹. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 410 nm were 2.79 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0033 µg Nb cm⁻², respectively. The metal ligand stoichiometry had been established by Job's method of continuous variation as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper to be 1 : 2 which was further confirmed by the mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the proposed procedure containing 10 µg Nb^V, the ions/complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts in aqueous phase (mg/10 ml amounts in parentheses) such as carbonate, bromide, iodide, sulfate, sulfite, chloride, EDTA, sulfosalicylic acid, tartrate, thiourea, acetate, dithionite and hydrogen carbonate (200 each); ascorbic acid (180); nitrite, nitrate, silicate, phosphate, boric acid and hydrazine sulfate (100 each); citrate (50); oxalate (20) and fluoride (1) caused an error of <1% in the recovery of niobium. Higher amounts of fluoride were tolerable in presence of boric acid. The cations : Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Be^{II}, Ca^{II}, Pb^{II}, Sr^{II}, As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Al^{III}, U^{VI}, Th^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Se^{IV}, Au^{III}, Ag^I and Cr^{VI} (1000 fold each); Bi^{III} (800 fold); Cr^{III} (400 fold); Os^{VIII} and Fe^{III,II} (100 fold each); Ir^{III} (80 fold); Ti^{IV} (70 fold); La^{III} (50 fold); Ta^V (40 fold); Zr^{IV} (20 fold); Re^{VII}, Pt^{IV}, Sn^{II} and Ru^{III} (10 fold each); Pd^{II} (5 fold) did not influence the absorbance of the complex and were tolerable. W^{VI}, V^V and Mo^{VI} could be tolerated in presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Applications : The proposed method is rapid, sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of metal ions including Ti, V, Fe, Mo, W, Re, U, Ta and platinum

metals which are generally found associated with Nb in natural samples and alloys. The usefulness of the method had been tested by analysing various synthetic samples of different compositions and reverberatory flue dust (Table 2).

Table 2. Analysis of niobium(V) in different samples

Sl. no.	Composition mg	Nb added µg	Nb found µg	
			Proposed method*	PAR ^I method**
1.	Mn(5), Co(2), Cu(2), Zn(2)	10.0	10.1 ± 0.73%	10.1
2.	Ir(0.2), Pt(0.01), Pd(0.01)	5.0	5.3 ± 0.93%	5.2
3.	Ca(5), Ba(5), Mg(2)	8.0	8.1 ± 0.58%	7.9
4.	Al(5), U(2), Cr ^{VI} (1)	2.0	2.1 ± 2.75%	2.0
5.	Cr ^{III} (1), Fe ^{III} (0.5), Co(5)	5.0	5.1 ± 1.47%	5.0
6.	Ce(2), Zr(0.05), Ta(0.1)	10.0	10.1 ± 0.47%	9.9
7.	Fe ^{II} (0.1), Th(5), Bi(2)	12.0	12.1 ± 0.36%	12.2
8.	Ru(0.01), Re(0.02), Be(5)	4.0	3.9 ± 1.83%	4.1
9.	W(0.1), Ir(0.5), Se(1) ^a	5.0	4.9 ± 1.2%	5.0
10.	Mo(0.01), Ti(0.1), Cu(5) ^b	10.0	9.9 ± 0.9%	10.1
11.	Ta(0.3), V(0.2) ^b	2.0	2.1 ± 3.55%	1.9
12.	Ta(0.01)	5.0	5.3 ± 1.2%	5.1
13.	Reverberatory flue dust (100)	2.0	2.2 ± 3.25%	2.3
		5.0	5.2 ± 1.47%	5.0
		10.0	10.3 ± 0.47%	9.8

*Mean ± %RSD (n=5). ** Average of duplicate analyses.

^aIn presence of 200 mg sodium potassium tartrate. ^bIn presence of 100 mg sodium dithionite.

The results obtained were in good agreement with the amount of Nb^V added initially and the relative standard deviation for the determination of 10 µg Nb^V for ten replicate analyses was 0.33%. The method compared favourably with the existing methods of niobium determination (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	Solvent λ_{\max} , nm	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ (Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Interfering metal ions
1.	Nb ^V , 4 M HClO ₄ , 3-hydroxyflavone, colour development time 3 min ^a	Chloroform (395)	4.09×10^4 (0.002)	Not known
2.	Nb ^V , 4 M HClO ₄ , 3-hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one, colour development time 2 min ^b	Dichloromethane (420)	5.04×10^4 (0.0018)	W ^{VI} (>15 μg), Mo ^{VI} (>5 μg)
3.	Nb ^V , 4 M HClO ₄ , 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-one, colour development time 2 min ^c	Chloroform (412)	4.79×10^4 (0.0019)	W ^{VI} (>20 μg), Mo ^{VI} (>4 μg)
4.	Nb ^V , <i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl- α -phenyl-styryl-acrylohydroxamic acid ^d	– (385)	3.7×10^4 (0.0025)	Not known
5.	Nb ^V , pH 1.0–4.0, tartaric acid, 2-(3,5-dibromo-2-pyridylazo)-5-diethylaminophenol (PADAP) ^e	– (630)	2.6×10^4 (0.0035)	Not known
6.	Nb ^V , 5-bromo-PADAP ^f	– (610)	4.2×10^4 (0.0022)	Not known
7.	Nb ^V , 0.5–1.0 M thiocyanate, 2.5–4.0 M HCl, (0.9–1.2) $\times 10^3$ M cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide, <i>N</i> -hydroxy- <i>N,N'</i> -diphenylbenzamidine ^g	Chloroform (390)	5.3×10^4 (0.0017)	Mo ^{VI}
8.	Present method	Chloroform (410)	2.79×10^4 (0.0033)	39 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 4. ^cRef. 5. ^dRef. 6. ^eRef. 7. ^fRef. 8. ^gRef. 12.

Experimental

Standard solution of niobium(V) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by fusing niobium pentoxide (0.1430 g), with potassium pyrosulfate¹ in a silica crucible. The melt was dissolved in hot 5% tartaric acid solution, cooled and made up to mark with the acid solution in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The solution thus obtained was standardized gravimetrically with cupferron¹⁰. Working solutions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level were prepared fresh daily by suitable dilution of the stock solution with 2% tartaric acid solution. Perchloric acid (Qualigens, "exclara") 8 M was prepared by diluting 70% (11.6 M) acid with deionized water. 6-Chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (CFHB), m.p. 198° was synthesized by the literature method¹¹ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.4% (w/v) solution. Chloroform (Qualigens, "SQ") was distilled and the fraction distilling at 60–61° was used. UV-VIS (Shimadzu-140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing niobium(V) solution with solutions of other metal ions in suitable proportions as shown in Table 2. Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) from copper manufacture unit containing no niobium

was mixed with a solution of known niobium content (1 mg) in a silica crucible. It was dried, fused with sodium peroxide, dissolved in water, neutralized with HClO₄ and final volume made to 100 ml in a volumetric flask. Aliquots (0.2, 0.5 and 1 ml) were taken for determination of niobium after adding sodium dithionite (100 mg) in each case.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing up to 13 μg of niobium and other ions were added 8 M perchloric acid (5 ml), 0.4% (w/v) CFHB (1 ml) and sufficient deionized water to make up the volume to 10 ml. The temperature of the solution was maintained at 25–35°. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform for 1 min. The layers were allowed to separate and the organic phase was poured over anhydrous sodium sulfate for removal of any retained water. The absorbance of the coloured complex was measured at 410 nm against a reagent blank and the amount of metal ion determined from a calibration graph in the range 1–13 μg Nb in 10 ml of the solution.

For 50 fold W^{VI} was added 20 mg sodium potassium tartrate and for each of 50 fold V^V and 10 fold Mo^{VI} was added 100 mg sodium dithionite, as masking agents, prior to the addition of CFHB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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